

Solvent Extraction Separation of Lead(II) with Macroyclic Polyethers

R. G. VIBHUTE and S. M. KHOPKAR*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay-400 076

Lead(II) was quantitatively extracted between pH 2 and 3 with 0.02 M DC 18-crown-6 in chloroform from 0.06 M picric acid as the counter ion. It was stripped with 0.5 M perchloric acid and was determined spectrophotometrically as its complex with Arsenazo III at 635 nm. It was separated from alkali, alkaline earths, uranium, copper, zinc, cadmium, bismuth, antimony and common anions. The process of selective stripping permits its separation from bismuth, antimony, thallium and tin. The method was extended for the analysis of lead from lead base alloys.

SOLVENT extraction separation of lead with macrocyclic polyethers was confined to the extractive photometric determination. Thus it was extracted with 18-crown-6 with eosin as an anion¹. It was also extracted with dibromo derivative of DB 18-crown-6 with bromothymol blue as the counterion². Sulphothalein dyes were effectively utilised as the counterion for the solvent extraction of lead with DB 18-crown-6³. Metanil yellow⁴ was also used for the extractive photometric determination of lead with 18-crown-6. Bis(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid⁵ was explored for the extraction of lead with DC 18-crown-6 in toluene. However, anionic basic dyes lack selectivity and as such large number of elements show serious interference. It was also extracted from nitric acid with DC 18-crown-6 in chloroform⁶. These complexes were polarographically analysed⁷ to ascertain their stability. The species formed during extraction of lead with 24-crown-8, metal to ligand ratio was 1 : 2⁸.

Cryptand 2.2.2 was used with eosin as the counter ion^{9,10}. So far no attempts have been made to utilise picric acid as the counter ion. It was extracted with DB 18-crown-6 from lithium picrate¹¹ to ascertain the composition of the extracted species. The systematic investigations on the solvent extraction separation of lead with DC 18-crown-6 with picrate as the counter ion is lacking. Such studies are therefore reported in this paper.

Experimental

An Orion Research Microprocessor Ion Analyser 901 with glass and calomel electrode and a ECIL GS 866C spectrophotometer with matched 10 mm corex glass cuvettes were used.

A stock solution of lead was prepared by appropriate dilution. Picric acid solution of 0.01 M was prepared. Crown ethers (0.02 M) were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of 12-crown-4, 15-crown-5, 18-crown-6, dicyclohexyl 18-crown-6,

dibenzo 18-crown-6, dibenzo 24-crown-8 (Aldrich) in chloroform.

General procedure: To an aliquot of solution containing lead (50 µg), picric acid was added to have its concentration 0.006 M in a total volume of 10 ml. pH of the resulting solution was adjusted at 2–4 with 0.01 M picric acid or lithium hydroxide solution. The solution was then transferred into a separatory funnel, 0.02 M solution (10 ml) of the appropriate crown ether in chloroform was added, and the flask shaken for 10 min. The two phases were allowed to settle and separate. The organic phase was withdrawn and equilibrated with 0.5 M perchloric acid (10 ml) to strip out lead in the aqueous phase. It was determined spectrophotometrically, as its Arsenazo III complex at 635 nm. The amount of lead present was calculated from a calibration graph.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH: The optimum pH for the quantitative extraction of lead was ascertained by extracting it with 0.02 M of various crown ethers at varying pH. The phase ratio was kept 1 : 1. The extraction was incomplete with 12-crown-4 and 15-crown-5 or DB 24-crown-8; however, with 18-crown-6, DB 18-crown-6 and DC 18-crown-6 the extraction was quantitative in the pH range 2–4 (Fig. 1). On account of broad pH range for extraction, DC 18-crown-6 was used throughout the work.

Effect of crown ether concentration: The optimum concentration of DC 18-crown-6 for the quantitative extraction of lead was ascertained by extracting lead with 10 ml of various concentrations of crown ether (1×10^{-3} – 4×10^{-3} M) (Table 1). The extraction was also carried out with varying volumes (2.5–20 ml) of 2×10^{-3} M DC 18-crown-6. The extraction was more than 80% with 1×10^{-3} M DC 18-crown-6 but it was quantitative with 1.5×10^{-3} M DC 18-crown-6. The varying volumes of the extractant showed incomplete extraction with

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on extraction of Pb(II); (x) 12-crown-4, (□) 15-crown-5, (○) DB 18-crown-6, (△) 18-crown-6, (●) DC 18-crown-6 and (■) DB 24-crown-8.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DC 18-CROWN-6 CONCENTRATION

DC 18-crown-6 $1 \times 10^{-3} M$	<i>E</i> %	<i>D</i>
3	32.5	0.48
4	39.5	0.65
5	42.5	0.73
6	55	1.2
7	66	1.95
8	70	2.3
9	75	3
10	80	4
15-40	100	∞

2.5–7.5 ml, but with 10 ml the extraction was quantitative. The optimum volume and concentration of the crown ether was 10 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ of DC 18-crown-6 in chloroform.

Effect of picric acid concentration : The concentration of picric acid for the quantitative extraction was ascertained by extracting lead(II) with varying concentrations of picric acid in the concentration range $1-10 \times 10^{-5} M$. The extraction was more than 35% with $1 \times 10^{-5} M$, 80% with 4.5×10^{-5} and 100% with $6 \times 10^{-5} M$. Therefore, $7 \times 10^{-5} M$ picric acid was used (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PICRIC ACID CONCENTRATION

Picric acid $1 \times 10^{-5} M$	<i>E</i> %	<i>D</i>
1	35	0.58
2	45	0.81
2.5	53	1.12
3	65	1.85
4	77	3.34
4.5	80	4
5	87	6.69
5.5	92	11.5
6-10	100	∞

Effect of counter ions : Eosin, zincon, bromothymol blue, metanil yellow, tropelin-OO and PAR

were used as the counterions for the extraction of lead. These counterions associate with cationic lead-crown ether complex to form uncharged ion-pair. No extraction was possible with eosin, zincon, PAR and bromothymol blue used as the counterions. While with tropelin-OO the extraction was 35% in the pH range 2–3 and with metanil yellow the extraction was quantitative in the pH range 3–4. The study with various mineral acids showed that with 5–7 *M* HNO₃ or with 4–5 *M* HCl extraction was quantitative. Throughout the investigation picric acid was preferred due to its planar structure and offered wide pH range for extraction.

Effect of diluents : Various diluents like benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, dichloromethane, dichloroethane and nitrobenzene were used as diluents for DC 18-crown-6 for the extraction of lead (Table 3). Chloroform was most

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF DILUENTS

Diluent	<i>E</i>	<i>E</i> %	<i>D</i>
Methylene chloride	9.08	95	19
Ethylene chloride	10.50	90	9
Carbon tetrachloride	2.24	100	∞
Toluene	2.30	45	0.81
Chloroform	4.80	100	∞
Hexane	1.9	0	0
Benzene	2.28	100	∞
Nitrobenzene	34.80	50	1

suitable for the purpose. The previous workers also preferred chloroform as a diluent for extraction of lead²⁻³ due to its better layer separation.

Effect of stripping agents : After extraction, lead was stripped with 10 ml of mineral acid (0.1–5*M*) as the stripping agents (Table 4). Perchloric acid (0.1–5*M*) offered the best results. Hydrochloric and acetic acids were effective from 3 to 5*M*. All other acids proved to be poor stripping agents. Thus 10 ml of 1*M* perchloric acid was used for routine work.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF STRIPPING AGENT

Compd. <i>M</i>	0.1	0.5	1	2	3	4	5
HClO ₄	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
HCl	40	50	62.2	78.5	100	100	100
HNO ₃	25	50	43	43	35	35	30
H ₂ SO ₄	0	15	20	71.4	64.2	60.7	58
OH ₃ COO	30	50	64.2	71.5	100	100	100

Effect of time of equilibration : The solution was shaken on wrist action flask shaker for varying time of shaking ranging from 2 to 10 min. The extraction was complete after 10 min of shaking. Hence 10 min shaking period was employed.

Effect of metal ion concentration : Different amount of lead 10–70 $\mu\text{g}/10 \text{ ml}$ was extracted at pH 3.0 with 10 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ DC 18-crown-6 in chloroform. The extraction was quantitative upto

60 µg/10 ml of lead. For higher concentration of metal it will be necessary to use higher concentration of crown ether.

Nature of extracted species: The nature of extracted species was ascertained from the plot of log *D* vs log [crown ether] at fixed picric acid concentration and plot of log *D* vs log [picric acid] at fixed DC 18-crown-6 concentration, where *D* represents the distribution ratio. The corresponding slopes were 1.42 and 2.45 respectively. Therefore, probable composition of the extracted species Pb-DC 18-crown-6-picric acid is 1 : 1 : 2. These findings are in agreement with those of the previous workers¹¹.

Effect of foreign ions: Lead(II) was extracted in presence of several foreign ions (Table 5). The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ion which causes an error of ±0.01 in the absorbance measurement. This approximately corresponds to ±2% error in the recovery of lead. Alkali metals were tolerated in ratio 1 : 5 while alkaline earths were tolerated in ratio 1 : 10. Indium, germanium and gallium were tolerated in the ratios 1 : 20 while copper, zinc, cadmium, mercury were tolerated in the ratio 1 : 500. The anions were tolerated in the ratio 1 : 500.

Separation of lead from multicomponent mixtures: It was possible to separate lead from various metal ions in multicomponent mixtures by the process of selective extraction. Antimony, thallium and bismuth were quantitatively extracted with DC 18-crown-6 along with lead at pH 2-4 and were stripped with 0.5 M H₂SO₄. While cadmium, germanium and tin were extracted after extraction of lead. Lead was first extracted with DC 18-crown-6 and stripped with 1 M perchloric acid. The unextracted cadmium, germanium or tin from the aqueous phase was directly determined. Various separations are summarised in Table 6.

Application to the analysis of lead base alloys: About 0.1 g of alloy was dissolved in aqua regia and

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Ion	Added as	Tolerance Limit µg
Li ⁺	LiCl	5500
Na ⁺	NaCl	250
K ⁺	KCl	100
Rb ⁺	RbCl	200
Ba ⁺⁺	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	1000
Mg ⁺⁺	MgCl ₂	1000
Ca ⁺⁺	CaCl ₂	500
Sr ⁺⁺	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	300
Ba ⁺⁺	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	400
Ga ⁺⁺	GaCl ₃	1200
In ⁺⁺	InCl ₃	1100
Tl ⁺⁺	TlCl ₃	100
Ge ⁺⁺	GeCl ₄	1500
Sn ⁺⁺	SnCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	200
Cu ⁺⁺	CuSO ₄	5000
Zn ⁺⁺	ZnSO ₄	1500
Cd ⁺⁺	3CdSO ₄ ·8H ₂ O	2500
Hg ⁺⁺	Hg(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	500
U ⁶⁺	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	1200
Ce ⁺⁺	(NH ₄) ₂ Ce(NO ₃) ₆	500
Cl ⁻	HCl	2500
Br ⁻	HBr	2000
I ⁻	HI	1800
NO ₃ ⁻	HNO ₃	2500
SO ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ SO ₄	1500
PO ₄ ³⁻	H ₃ PO ₄	2200
ClO ₄ ⁻	HClO ₄	1200
CH ₃ COO ⁻	CH ₃ COOH	3000
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	2500
Tartrate	Tartaric acid	2000
Ascorbate	Ascorbic acid	2500

tin was precipitated and removed as metastannic acid. An aliquot of solution containing lead along with cadmium, zinc, copper was extracted with DC 18-crown-6 at pH 3.0 when only lead was extracted. When bismuth was present along with lead, it was co-extracted with lead but it can be selectively stripped with 0.5 M H₂SO₄ followed by stripping of lead with 1M perchloric acid. The results showed the amount of lead in percentage actually found against that present shown in parenthesis: gun metal, 5.8 (5.75); woods metal, 26.2 (26.1); lead-

TABLE 6—SEPARATIONS FROM MULTICOMPONENT MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Elements	Amount taken µg	Amount found µg	Extractant	Stripping agent	Sequence of extraction
1.	Sb	100	100	DC 18-crown-6	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ 1M HClO ₄	First
	Pb	50	44	DC 18-crown-6		Second
	Ge	200	200	No extraction		Last
2.	Sb	50	50	DC 18-crown-6	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ 1M HClO ₄	First
	Pb	50	47	DC 18-crown-6		Second
	In	100	100	No extraction		Last
3.	Bi	100	100	DC 18-crown-6	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ 1 M HClO ₄	First
	Pb	50	46	DC 18-crown-6		Second
	SnIV	50	52	No extraction		Last
4.	TiIII	100	100	DC 18-crown-6	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ 1 M HClO ₄	First
	Pb	50	45	DC 18-crown-6		Second
	Cd	200	200	No extraction		Last
5.	Sb	100	100	DC 18-crown-6	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ 1 M HClO ₄	First
	Pb	50	46	DC 18-crown-6		Second
	SnIV	50	50	No extraction		Last

bismuth alloy, 93.5 (93.0) ; bismuth solder, 27.0 (26.8) ; and brass 1.70 (1.68).

The proposed method is simple, rapid and selective. The total time required for separation and determination is 2 h. The separation of lead from bismuth, antimony, tin, germanium is significant because these are associated with lead base alloys.

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